

APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS TO FORECAST THE YIELD OF GRAIN CROPS

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Abstract. This article presents the development of an AI model and a software tool designed to predict the yield of grain crops using Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and a dataset from kaggle.com. The research focuses on analyzing a variety of environmental, climatic, and agricultural factors that influence crop productivity. By leveraging regression techniques, the model aims to provide accurate yield forecasts based on historical data and real-time inputs. The software tool developed offers a user-friendly interface for farmers and agricultural professionals, enabling them to make informed decisions regarding resource management, crop selection, and harvest planning. The model effectiveness is evaluated through empirical testing such as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE) highlighting its potential for improving agricultural efficiency and food security.

Keywords: machine learning, root mean squared error, mean absolute error, mean squared error, linear regression, multiple linear regression, random forest.

The growing global demand for food, coupled with the increasing challenges posed by climate change, makes the accurate prediction of crop yields more important than ever. Agricultural productivity is influenced by numerous factors, including soil quality, weather patterns, agricultural practices, and the genetic traits of crops. Understanding and predicting crop yields allows for better resource allocation, improved planning, and enhanced food security. By leveraging large datasets that include historical yields, environmental conditions, and real-time inputs, regression-based models can provide more precise and actionable insights for farmers and agricultural stakeholders [8]. The development of the AI model and software tool for prediction grain crop yields is based on a structured, multi-phase methodology like ML algorithms and data preprocessing techniques.

Linear Regression is a simple but powerful algorithm widely used in machine learning and statistics. It helps predict output values based on given input data by modeling a linear relationship between two variables. The main purpose of linear regression is to find the line that best describes the relationship between given input data (independent variables) and output data (dependent variable). This line is represented by the following mathematical model [2]:

$$y = b_0 + b_1 * x + \varepsilon$$

Here:

- y is the dependent variable (predicted value).
- x is an independent variable (input value).
- b_0 — intercept (intersection point of the line along the y axis).
- b_1 — slope (angle of deviation of the line).

- ε — is the error or residual (the random component associated with the accuracy of the model).

Linear regression helps to explain commonly found relationships among people. Because it takes the input variables right-handed when determining each person's value, and finds a linear curve corresponding to them. Linear regression is effective for data that uses a significant number of variables. This helps in identifying dependencies in data analysis. The main reason for this is that when using it, the variables are taken as true, and linear regression fitting works best on variables of true quality.

Random Forests are widely utilized supervised machine learning algorithm that proves effective in addressing regression and classification challenges. Notably, it often delivers commendable results without requiring extensive hyper-parameter tuning, making it a popular choice. Its simplicity is a key characteristic, as it involves building multiple decision trees on different samples and then combining their outputs through a majority vote for classification problems. This algorithm's adaptability and efficiency have contributed to its widespread use across diverse machine learning applications. In this sphere that we are doing experiment, classification algorithms are basic tool to predict a crop type that farmers plant next season their field [6]. The final output is then determined based on the majority votes of these predictions, exemplifying the collaborative and democratic nature of the random forest algorithm (fig.1). The predictive performance of the models was evaluated using a mean absolute error (MAE), and a root mean squared error (RMSE), while a separate dataset was used to test and verify the selected model. The test included assessing the performance of each prediction model on a separate dataset and generating graphs to compare the predicted and actual values of crop yield such as changing temperature, rainfall. For regression problems MAE and RMSE metrics are most implemented. In this section we compare the results taken from four models through MAE and RMSE according to mentioned four algorithms in section above.

Figure 1. Correlation coefficients of features.

The development of this crop yield prediction tool based on regression algorithms demonstrates significant progress in integrating data science with agriculture. While challenges such as data quality and computational demands persist, the tool offers tangible benefits to farmers, policymakers, and researchers alike. Continued advancements in data integration,

machine learning, and software scalability will further enhance the system's accuracy and utility, making it a valuable asset for global food production and sustainability efforts.

Performance Metrics: Evaluation was based on statistical measures such as MSE, MAE, RMSE with a focus on minimizing error and maximizing the model's generalizability across different crops and regions. **Field Testing:** The software was tested in real-world agricultural settings by simulating various environmental scenarios and comparing the predicted yields with actual harvest data [11].

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$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_{act} - y_{pred}| \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_{act} - y_{pred})^2}{n}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

n is the number of data points,

y_{pred} is the predicted value of the dependent variable for the i^{th} data point,

y_{act} is the actual value of the dependent variable for the i^{th} data point.

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